

Increasing the Turnover of MSMEs in Healthy Beverages Through Digital Marketing Strategies: A Case Study of Shuguci and WHF MSMEs

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Keywords: Digital Marketing; Digital Marketing Funnel; MSMEs; Brand Awareness; Revenue Growth.	Abstrak
Submitted: 13/05/2025	<p>This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of applying Digital Marketing strategies in increasing the revenue and brand awareness of the Healthy Beverage MSMEs, Shuguci and WHF. The method used is qualitative with a case study approach, where data were collected through observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation of the MSMEs' digital marketing activities. The results show that after the mentoring program, the MSMEs' revenue increased by 50%, accompanied by improved understanding among owners and employees regarding digital marketing strategies. They are now more adept at using hashtags, determining optimal posting times, segmenting markets, and utilizing trending music in digital content. Additionally, customer interaction significantly improved, as indicated by the growing number of customers reaching out via direct messages during promotions and actively participating in live sessions on social media. The referral program offering discounts to customers who recommended the products also proved effective in increasing the number of new customers. It can be concluded that implementing Digital Marketing strategies can be an effective solution for MSMEs to increase their revenue and brand awarene</p>
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INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are the main pillars of the Indonesian economy, playing a central role in creating jobs, developing the local economy, and driving innovation and community empowerment. Data shows that more than 99 percent of business units in Indonesia are MSMEs, with around 66 million business actors in 2023 (Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs, 2023). Their contribution to national economic growth is very significant, especially in the food and

beverage sector, which dominates around 53.94 percent of the total products marketed through digital platforms. In today's digital era, the main challenge for MSMEs is the ability to adapt quickly to market and technological changes. Digitalization is one of the main solutions to increase competitiveness and expand market reach. A study conducted by INDEF shows that 88.37 percent of MSMEs that initially operated offline experienced an increase in turnover after utilizing digital platforms (INDEF, 2024). Of that number, 66.28 percent experienced an annual increase in turnover of up to 50 percent. This shows that the use of digital marketing strategies has great potential in driving the growth of MSMEs (INDEF, 2024, p. 2).

MSMEs Healthy Drinks Shuguci and WHF are examples of business actors in the beverage sector who have utilized digital platforms such as e-commerce and social media in their marketing strategies. However, even though they have adopted digital marketing, their monthly turnover has not yet reached the target expected by the business owner. Therefore, more intensive assistance is needed in managing digital marketing strategies, including optimizing social media, marketing content, and managing digital advertising campaigns.

Based on this urgency, this community service program is designed to provide digital marketing training and mentoring for Shuguci and WHF MSMEs. This program aims to improve the skills of business owners in managing digital marketing more effectively, expanding market reach, and increasing their sales turnover. The results of this program are expected to be a model that can be replicated by other MSMEs in facing challenges and opportunities in the digital era.

Digital marketing has become an important element in modern marketing strategies, especially for MSMEs who want to expand their market reach. One concept that is widely used to understand consumer behavior in digital marketing is the Digital Marketing Funnel, developed by Kotler and Armstrong (2019). This model describes the stages of the customer journey from the first stage of getting to know a product to becoming a loyal customer.

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2019), the Digital Marketing Funnel consists of several main stages. First awareness: At this stage, potential customers first become acquainted with the brand or product through various digital channels such as social media, online advertising, or search engine optimization (SEO). In the context of MSMEs, the use of social media such as Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok is a key strategy in increasing brand awareness.

Second, consideration: After realizing the existence of the product, potential customers start looking for more information. MSMEs can increase the appeal of their products by presenting customer reviews, product videos, or educational content that provides added value to consumers. Third, conversion: This stage is the point at which potential customers decide to make a purchase. Strategies such as discounts, limited promotions, and ease of payment and shipping methods are very influential in increasing sales conversions.

Fourth, loyalty: After making a purchase, maintaining relationships with customers is important to increase their loyalty. Strategies such as loyalty programs, responsive customer service, and active interaction on social media can help MSMEs retain their customers. Fifth, advocacy: Customers who are satisfied with products and services can become natural promoters by recommending products to others. MSMEs can encourage this advocacy by holding referral programs or providing incentives for customers who provide positive reviews and share their experiences on social media.

Previous studies have shown that digital marketing funnels can increase the effectiveness of digital marketing, especially for MSMEs that are still in the development stage (Chaffey & Smith, 2022). In a study conducted by INDEF (INDEF, 2024, p. 4), more than 88.37 percent of MSMEs experienced an increase in turnover after adopting digital marketing strategies, including through social media and e-commerce platforms.

In the context of Shuguci and WHF Healthy Drink MSMEs, the implementation of a digital marketing funnel can help optimize their digital marketing strategies. Currently, both MSMEs have used digital platforms for marketing, but their turnover has not met the set target. Therefore, through assistance based on the Digital Marketing Funnel model, it is hoped that MSMEs can be more effective in attracting new customers, increasing sales conversions, and retaining loyal customers for the long term.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative method with a case study approach. This approach was chosen to gain an in-depth understanding of the implementation of the Digital Marketing Funnel strategy in increasing the turnover of Shuguci and WHF Healthy Drink MSMEs. Case studies allow for detailed exploration of the experiences, challenges, and effectiveness of digital marketing strategies implemented by these MSMEs (Yin, 2018). This study was conducted at Shuguci and WHF Healthy Drink MSMEs located in Bandung Kidul District, Bandung City. The subjects of the study included: MSME owners as decision makers in digital marketing strategies, employees involved in digital marketing operations, and customers as end users who interact with MSME digital marketing strategies. The data in this study were collected through several techniques, first, participatory observation by observing MSME digital marketing activities, including the use of social media, content strategies, and customer responses to digital campaigns that were run. Second, conducting in-depth interviews with MSME owners and marketing teams to understand the challenges and effectiveness of the digital marketing strategies that have been implemented. Third, documentation by collecting data from social media posts, sales reports, and customer interactions on various digital platforms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the mentoring, based on interviews with the owner and marketing employees, several changes were found, namely:

Increase in Turnover after Digital Marketing Mentoring

After the implementation of digital marketing mentoring, Shuguci and WHF Healthy Drink UMKM experienced a 50% increase in turnover compared to the period before mentoring. This increase shows that a digital marketing strategy based on the Digital Marketing Funnel (Kotler & Armstrong, 2019) can effectively increase UMKM sales. The main factors contributing to this increase are the optimization of social media and the implementation of a more targeted digital marketing strategy, including the use of relevant hashtags, choosing optimal broadcast times, and an in-depth understanding of market segmentation.

If so far Shuguci and WHF have only created content to suit trends, after mentoring, they carried out clear and targeted planning, one of which was determining consumer segmentation. Based on the results of consumer research that overlaps with Shuguci and WHF geographically must be in Bandung, for the time being Shuguci delivery cannot be done between cities, because the type of drink that must be at a minimum cold temperature of seppuku degrees. Demographically defined, their consumers are women with an age range of 24-60 years, and have an income of 5 to 10 million per month. Psychographically, they are people who are educated about health, for example low-sugar drinks, fruits that can prevent cholesterol and diabetes. Based on this analysis, the team created content that had been adjusted including taking into account the time when target consumers would open Instagram. Although based on general research, uploads must be done at 9, 12, and 15. This does not apply to Shuguci and WHF, they upload content at 4-5 pm, because their segmentation is workers who have free hours around 4-7 pm.

Increased Brand Awareness

One of the positive impacts of this mentoring is the increased understanding of MSME owners and employees about the importance of brand awareness. Before this program, the digital marketing strategy implemented was still limited to regular uploads without strategic content planning. However, after mentoring, owners and employees understand how to build a brand image through the following techniques: first, the use of the Right Hashtag: First, the team ensures that each upload uses a hashtag that is in accordance with the target market so that it is easier for potential customers to find, for example, the hashtags that are often used are #healthydrinks #healthylife #lessugar. The use of this hashtag aims to make the Shuguci and WHF brands known as beverage brands that are very concerned with Health.

Second, determining the optimal broadcast hours: Based on social media insight analysis, uploads are made at times with the highest interaction, such as morning (07.00-09.00) and afternoon (16.00-18.00), and the right broadcast hours for Shuguci and WHF are 16.00-18.00. Third, understanding market segments: content is tailored to customer preferences, for example highlighting the health benefits of Shuguci and WHF for consumers who care about a healthy lifestyle. Fourth, selecting trending songs for video content: Using viral music to increase engagement on platforms such as TikTok and Instagram Reels

Better Customer Interaction

In addition to increasing turnover, this assistance also contributed to increasing customer interaction with the Shuguci and WHF brands. This can be seen from the following indicators: first, more customers contact via DM (Direct Message): When there is a certain promotion, the number of customers asking for product details and prices increases significantly. This shows that the promotional strategy implemented has succeeded in attracting the attention of potential buyers.

Second, greeting subscribers during live social media: live streaming on Instagram and TikTok is one of the methods used to increase customer engagement. Business owners actively greet old customers who attend live sessions, which makes them feel closer to the Shuguci and WHF brands.

Referral Program: Discounts for Customers Who Recommend Shuguci and WHF

As part of the Advocacy-based marketing strategy in the Digital Marketing Funnel, MSMEs implement a discount program for customers who successfully recommend products to others. This program has proven effective in increasing the number of new customers because customers feel compelled to promote the product to their friends or family. Shuguci and WHF specialize this program for customers who order regularly every week, the team will give small gifts, or discounts for certain products. In addition to maintaining loyalty, this also increases the desire of customers to recommend Shuguci and WHF products to their colleagues.

Evaluation and Challenges Faced

Although the results of this mentoring show a positive impact, there are several challenges that still need to be overcome, including: first, consistency in managing social media: Business owners still need to continue to practice maintaining content consistency so that customer interaction is maintained. The owner stated that it was very difficult to run for 1 week at the beginning, because they had to learn and recognize the same consumers and products. Second, time management between production and marketing: considering that this business is still small-scale with limited workforce, dividing time between production and digital marketing is still a challenge for the owner. At this stage, although Shuguci and WHF already have a media marketing team, in fact, their work is still overlapping with production, it is very important for the owner to explain the scope of work so that everything can be done.

Implications of Results for Other MSMEs' Strategies

The success of Shuguci and WHF MSMEs in increasing turnover and brand awareness through digital marketing shows that the Digital Marketing Funnel-based approach can be replicated by other MSMEs. By implementing the right strategy—starting from optimizing social media, more active interaction with customers, to referral programs—MSMEs can expand their market reach and increase competitiveness in the food and beverage industry.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that the implementation of the Digital Marketing Funnel strategy can effectively improve the digital marketing performance of MSMEs. The mentoring carried out on MSMEs Shuguci Healthy Drinks and WHF contributed to a 50% increase in turnover, which shows that optimizing social media and digital-based marketing strategies have a real impact on increasing sales.

In addition to increasing turnover, this mentoring has also succeeded in increasing brand awareness among MSME owners and employees. They now better understand important elements in digital marketing, such as the use of relevant hashtags, choosing optimal broadcast times, understanding market segments, and utilizing music trends in digital content. This understanding helps MSMEs build a stronger brand image and attract new customers.

Interaction with customers has also increased significantly. This is indicated by the increasing number of customers contacting MSMEs via direct message (DM) after the promotion, as well as increasing customer involvement in live sessions on social media. Referral programs with discounts for customers who recommend products have also proven effective in attracting new customers and increasing the loyalty of old customers.

Although the results of this mentoring show success, several challenges still need to be overcome, such as consistency in social media management and time management between production and digital marketing. Therefore, further mentoring and strengthening of digital marketing strategies are still needed to ensure the long-term growth of Shuguci and WHF MSMEs. This success can be an example for other MSMEs in implementing a more structured digital marketing strategy. By utilizing the right digital marketing, MSMEs can increase their competitiveness in the digital era and expand their market reach more effectively.

Suggestion

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been carried out, several suggestions that can be given for the development of Shuguci and WHF MSMEs and future research are as follows: first, consistency in producing and publishing digital content. It is recommended to create a structured monthly content calendar to ensure that content remains relevant, interesting, and well-scheduled according to audience segmentation. Second, optimization of social media analytics data by utilizing the analytics features available on social media platforms to continuously monitor content performance, understand audience behavior, and evaluate the effectiveness of broadcast hours, types of content, and hashtag use.

Third, advanced digital marketing training for MSME owners and employees needs to take advanced training on digital marketing, such as paid advertising strategies (Facebook Ads, Instagram Ads), copywriting, brand storytelling, and optimization of social media algorithms to increase reach and conversion. Fourth, diversify digital marketing channels by expanding the presence of Shuguci and WHF MSMEs in other marketplaces, instant messaging applications (such as WhatsApp Business), and optimizing simple websites or landing pages to strengthen business credibility.

For future research, it is recommended to conduct a comparative study with other MSMEs that apply different digital marketing approaches. In addition, the effectiveness

of each stage of the Digital Marketing Funnel can also be analyzed for various types of MSME products to enrich practical and academic insights.

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